

ANALYTIC METHODS TO PREDICT RESIN POCKET GEOMETRY AROUND THE MICROVASCULE IN SELF-HEALING COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Two analytic methods are presented to predict the resin pocket geometry around the microvascule in self-healing composites with microvascular networks. The bending strain energy is calculated on the fiber scale in one method (FSM), while is on the layer scale in the other method (LSM). For the FSM, several fibers in thickness direction are tied together to account for the bending stiffness increment caused by the interaction between the fibers. And for the LSM, a single ply is divided into several sublayers to account for the bending stiffness decrement caused by the sliding between adjacent fibers. Both analytic methods can provide the closed-form solution for the resin pocket width, and the analytic results agree well with experimental results. The physical consistency of two methods is proved. It is found that the resin pocket size depends mainly on ply angles of the plies close to microvascule, and the stacking sequence has some effect.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRPCs) are widely used in flight vehicles because of their high specific strength and modulus, performance designability and other advantages. Even so, their effective application in practical structure is still limited by some factors, such as damage resistance [1, 2], reparability and so on. The damage in composite structures is hard to inspect visually, but may degrade the composite performance. So it usually needs to be repaired. At present, damage in composites may be fixed through traditional mechanical or bonded repair methods [3, 4], but such repair requires temporary decommission of the damaged parts, collection of repair materials, and employee time and effort to enact the repair.

Inspired by the self-healing mechanism of living things after injury, researchers proposed the concept of self-healing composites in 1993 to solve these problems [5, 6]. There are three primary self-healing approaches now [7, 8], including intrinsic, capsule-based and vascular methods. Microvascular self-healing composites are extensively studied because they can repair large scale damage repeatedly.

Because of continuous plies, the microvascules located in the FRPCs are usually surrounded by a lenticular resin pocket as shown in Figure 1. This resin pocket is detrimental since it acts as a large crack-like interlaminar discontinuity in the composites and leads to interlaminar damage easily under mechanical loads [9-11]. The shape and size of the resin pocket are important since they govern the local stress and strain fields, which depend on composite laminate parameters (such as stacking sequence), ply material properties and curing pressure, etc. But few investigations have been conducted to predict the resin pocket geometry in the microvascular self-healing composites.

Figure 1: Microscopic image of resin pocket around the microvascule in FRPCs.

The formation process of the resin pockets in the microvascular self-healing composites is similar to that in the composites with embedded optical fibers, both of which are due to the introduction of inclusions. The only difference is that the inclusions in the microvascular self-healing composites must be taken away after curing, which perturbs the resin pocket geometry little. So the methods to predict the resin pocket geometry for the composites with embedded optical fibers can be referred to for the microvascular self-healing composites. Several researchers investigated the geometry of the resin pocket around the embedded optical fiber in composites. Dasgupta et al. presented an analytic method to determine the resin pocket geometry based on Rayleigh-Ritz method [12]. They employed a series of beam bending functions as assumed trial functions to approximate the resin pocket geometry. In their research, the composite was treated as a bundle of unconnected discrete fibers, and the bending strain energy and compressive strain energy of each fiber with a diameter of 6 μm were calculated. The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm with a user-supplied Jacobian was used to solve the highly nonlinear equations, and good correspondence with microscopic images was achieved. Later, they improved the method by considering the shear strain energy of the composite laminate [13]. But the method may underestimate the size of the resin pocket because the interaction between the fibers due to the friction and resin viscosity was not considered, which can increase composite ply bending stiffness. Case and Carman modified the energy formulation presented by Dasgupta and employed a cosinusoidal function as the trial function [14]. The resulting simplifications allowed the author to extract an analytical expression of the resin pocket geometry. However, in their research, the bending

energy of the laminate was calculated as $U_b = \frac{1}{2} \int_V E_x \left(\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 y^2 dV$ with variable stiffness to account for

different orientations of plies. This effectively means that the reinforcing fibers are bound together and the entire laminate is regarded as one solid part under bending deformation. It is well known that the bending stiffness of uncured laminate is much lower because of the sliding between adjacent fibers, which was also pointed out by Lammens et al. [15]. Lammens et al. presented a finite element technique to predict the resin pocket geometry surrounding the optical fiber in composites [15]. Later, they improved their method to account for the prediction of resin pocket geometry around inclusions with arbitrary shape [16]. In their research, a single ply was modeled as a stack of individual sublayers held together by friction to decouple the in-plane behavior of the ply from the bending behavior. To determine the parameters used by finite element analysis, a simple cantilever test was performed, in which a single ply was heated to the curing temperature and allowed to bend under the influence of gravity. Finally, 12 sublayers were validated to be the best for a single ply and a good agreement with microscopic images was achieved. However, the convergence of the model is not easy to get because some configurations, such as the element selection, hourglass control and contact setting, need to be adjusted. Personal correspondence with Lammens revealed that they also spent numerous hours improving the model before finally finding the correct way to get convergence.

In this paper, two analytic methods are developed to predict resin pocket geometry around the microvascules in self-healing composites with microvascular networks. One calculates the bending strain energy on the fiber scale (FSM). The other one is on the layer scale (LSM). The relation

between two methods is investigated, and the influence of the stacking sequence on the resin pocket geometry is explored.

2 METHOD ON THE FIBER SCALE (FSM)

The process of the resin pocket formation is highly nonlinear, involving transitions of the polymer matrix from viscous to viscoplastic to viscoelastic and finally to an elastic state as it progresses through various stages of the curing process. During initial curing stage, the bending stiffness of the reinforcing fibers determines the shape because the matrix is almost viscous. While the transverse compressive stiffness of composite ply further perturbs the shape during final curing stage. So the bending strain energy of the fibers and compressive strain energy of composite plies are considered here. To account for the bending stiffness increment caused by the interaction between the fibers due to the friction and resin viscosity, m fibers in thickness direction are considered tied together and bending together, and the number m will be decided later. The principal of minimum potential energy is employed to solve equations and to provide a closed-form solution of the resin pocket width.

2.1 Analytic procedure to predict resin pocket geometry

The potential energy Π of the whole part is given by the difference between the strain energy U and the work W done by applied load, i.e.,

$$\Pi = U - W \quad (1)$$

where U includes the bending strain energy U_{bf} of the fibers and compressive strain energy U_c of composite plies, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} U &= U_{bf} + U_c \\ &= \sum \frac{1}{2} \int_0^a \cos^2 \theta E_f I \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial s^2} \right)^2 ds + \frac{1}{2} E_y \int_V \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right)^2 dV \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the composite fibers are treated as discrete rods and the formula for calculating the bending strain energy of a beam is employed; E_f is the Young's modulus of the fiber; I is the inertia moment of m fibers tied together in thickness direction, which will be discussed later; v is the displacement trial field; s is the position in the fiber direction; E_y is the transverse compression modulus of each composite ply. Other parameters will be explained in the following contents.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the resin pocket.

A schematic diagram of the resin pocket is shown in Figure 2. In this paper, a quarter part is taken as the domain for numerical modelling, as shown in Figure 3. Figure 3(a) and Figure 3(b) show the relative position of composite plies and microvascule before and after curing respectively. The coordinate system origin is set at the peak of the microvascule. The x-axis is located in the ply plane

and perpendicular to the microvascule. Half the resin pocket width is a , and h is the total thickness of the composite plies above the microvascule before curing. The length of the domain along the z direction is assumed to be unit 1. r_0 is the radius of the microvascule. From Figure 3(b), the boundary conditions of the composite fibers in the domain of analysis are followings:

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0, y \in [0, h] \quad (3)$$

$$v = -\frac{h_c}{h} y \quad \text{at } x = 0, y \in [0, h] \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = a, y \in [0, h] \quad (5)$$

$$v = -r_0 \left(1 - \frac{y}{h}\right) - \frac{h_c}{h} y \quad \text{at } x = a, y \in [0, h] \quad (6)$$

where h_c is the displacement of the top surface during curing process, as shown in Figure 3(b).

Figure 3: Domain for numerical modeling with relative position of composite plies and microvascule, (a) before curing and (b) after curing.

The displacement trial field is assumed to vary linearly with respect to the y coordinate, so it is assumed to be:

$$v = \Phi \left(1 - \frac{y}{h}\right) - \frac{h_c}{h} y \quad (7)$$

$$\Phi = 24r_0 \left[-\frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{6} \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^3 - \frac{1}{24} \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^4 \right] \quad (8)$$

where Φ is the analytic expression to describe the resin pocket geometry and is assumed to be a beam function under uniform load, which is modified to make the displacement trial field v meet the boundary conditions.

Due to the bending strain energy U_{bf} of the fibers is calculated along the fiber direction s , while the displacement trial field v is an analytic expression about x and y , it must be transformed into an expression about s and y . To make the transformation universal, the ply angle is assumed to be θ ($\theta \neq 90^\circ, U_{bf} = 0$ when $\theta = 90^\circ$), as shown in Figure 4. The domain of analysis in Figure 4(a) can be transformed into the one in Figure 4(b), in which all the fibers have the same length ($a/\cos\theta$). The position along the x direction can be expressed with s by the equation

$$x = s \cdot \cos\theta \quad (9)$$

Then the displacement trial field v can be transformed into the form $v = f(s, y)$.

Figure 4: Domain of analysis with ply angle $\theta(\theta \neq 90^\circ)$, (a) before and (b) after transformed.

The fibers are assumed to be distributed evenly within the laminate and surrounded by polymer matrix, as shown in Figure 5(a). A unit cell containing only one fiber and surrounding matrix is shown in Figure 5(b), and the width l_f of the unit is calculated by $V_f = \pi \cdot r_f^2 / l_f^2$, where V_f is the fiber volume fraction of the composite laminate, and r_f is the radius of the fiber.

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of (a) fibers surrounded by polymer matrix and (b) a unit cell.

As mentioned before, to account for the bending stiffness increment caused by the interaction between the fibers due to the friction and resin viscosity, m fibers in thickness direction are tied and bend together, and I in Equation (2) denotes the inertia moment of m fibers tied together in thickness direction.

The compressive strain energy U_c of the composite plies is calculated by volume integral for the domain of analysis, i.e.

$$U_c = \frac{1}{2} E_y \int_V \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right)^2 dV = \frac{1}{2} E_y \int_0^h \int_0^a \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right)^2 dx dy \quad (10)$$

The work W done by applied load is computed as:

$$W = qh_c \quad (11)$$

$$q = p \cdot a \cdot 1 \quad (12)$$

where p is the curing pressure on the top surface of the domain of analysis.

After all the calculations above, the potential energy Π of the domain of analysis can be expressed with respect to a and h_c . In order to facilitate the stability of the numerical computational scheme, the width a is normalized with respect to the radius r_0 of the microvascule ($a^* = a/r_0$). Based on the principal of minimum potential energy, the following two equations are obtained.

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial a^*} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial h_c} = 0 \quad (14)$$

After simplification, there is only one unknown h_c in Equation (14), so the closed-form solution for h_c can be obtained. Substituting the value of h_c into Equation (13), the closed-form solution for a^* is also obtained. All of the calculating procedures are completed automatically with Matlab code.

2.2 Resin pocket geometry prediction

In order to validate this method, the experimental results in Ref. 12 are referred to. The material properties, geometric parameters and other parameters are listed in Table 1.

Item	Value
E_f : Young's modulus of composite fiber	230GPa
E_y : Transverse compression modulus of composite layer	11.4GPa
r_0 : Radius of the microvascule	40 μ m
r_f : Radius of the composite fiber	3 μ m
h_i : Thickness of a single ply	0.127mm
p : Curing pressure	0.69MPa
V_f : Fiber volume fraction of composite laminate	0.6

Table 1: Parameters used by the analytic methods [12].

To determine the value of m , the number indicates how many fibers in thickness direction are tied together, several values are tested and corresponding results of a^* are compared with experimental result for the stacking sequence $[60_2/30_2/(r_0)/30_2/60_2]$ ((r_0) denotes the location of microvascule). It was found that the analytic result of a^* just falls into the range of experimental results with $m = 5$. Figure 6 shows the corresponding geometry of resin pocket. Therefore, $m = 5$ is employed for the following research.

Figure 6: Geometry of resin pocket for the stacking sequence $[60_2/30_2/(r_0)/30_2/60_2]$.

The geometries of resin pocket for some other stacking sequences are predicted and compared with experimental results, as shown in Table 2. It can be found that all the analytic results fall in the range of corresponding experimental results except the result for stacking sequence $[45_4/(r_0)/45_4]$, for which the analytic result (7.46) is very close to the minimum experimental result (7.50). Therefore, the

proposed analytic method is effective to predict the resin pocket geometry around the microvascule in composites.

Stacking sequence	Experimental results	Analytic results
[90 ₂ /0 ₂ /(<i>r</i> ₀)/0 ₂ /90 ₂]	10.00~11.25	10.20
[75 ₂ /15 ₂ /(<i>r</i> ₀)/15 ₂ /75 ₂]	9.05~10.00	9.86
[45 ₄ /(<i>r</i> ₀)/45 ₄]	7.50~8.75	7.46
[30 ₂ /60 ₂ /(<i>r</i> ₀)/60 ₂ /30 ₂]	5.95~6.50	6.27
[15 ₂ /75 ₂ /(<i>r</i> ₀)/75 ₂ /15 ₂]	5.65~6.45	6.10

Table 2: Comparison of experimental results and analytic results with $m = 5$ [12].

3 METHOD ON THE LAYER SCALE (LSM)

The method on the layer scale (LSM) to predict the resin pocket geometry is similar to the FSM except the calculation of bending strain energy. In the FSM, the bending strain energy is calculated based on the composite fibers which are treated as discrete rods. But in the LSM, the bending strain energy is calculated based on sublayers divided from a single ply to account for the bending stiffness decrement caused by the sliding of adjacent fibers.

3.1 Analytic procedure to predict resin pocket geometry

The domain of analysis is same as that in the FSM, and Equation (1) is still applicable to represent the potential energy Π . The calculating procedures of the compressive strain energy U_c and the work W done by applied load are also same. Only the calculation of the bending strain energy U_{bsl} of the composite sublayers is explained in detail here.

The bending strain energy U_{bsl} of the composite sublayers is calculated as

$$U_{bsl} = \Sigma \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\frac{a}{\cos\theta}} EI_s \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial s^2} \right)^2 ds \quad (15)$$

where E is the Young's modulus of uncured composite laminate along the fiber direction, which is $E = E_f V_f$. I_s is the inertia moment of a composite sublayer, which will be discussed later in this section.

Due to the bending strain energy U_{bsl} is still calculated along the fiber direction s , the displacement trial field v must be transformed into an expression about s and y . Figure 7 shows a general case with a ply angle θ ($\theta \neq 90^\circ$). The domain of analysis in Figure 7(a) can be transformed into the form in Figure 7(b), and then into the form in Figure 7(c), where the fiber direction of the composite ply is perpendicular to the microvascule. Thus the integral range of s is 0 to $a/\cos\theta$, and the width perpendicular to the fiber is $l = 1 \cdot \cos\theta$.

Figure 7: Domain of analysis with ply angle θ ($\theta \neq 90^\circ$), (a) original state, (b) after one transformation, and (c) after two transformation.

Because a single ply is divided into several sublayers, the inertia moment I_s of an individual sublayer should be used. It is assumed that a ply is divided into m_s sublayers, so the thickness of a sublayer is $h_s = h_l / m_s$. I_s can be obtained as $I_s = l \cdot h_s^3 / 12$.

The solving process of the unknown a^* and h_c is the same as that in the FSM.

3.2 Resin pocket geometry prediction

The same objective as the FSM is used here in order to compare these two methods conveniently. To determine the sublayer number m_s , several values are tested and corresponding results of a^* are compared with experimental result for the stacking sequence $[60_2/30_2/(r_0)/30_2/60_2]$. It was found that the analytic result of a^* just falls into the range of experimental results with $m_s = 4$. So $m_s = 4$ is employed for the following research.

The geometries of resin pocket for some other stacking sequences are predicted and compared with experimental results, as shown in Table 3. It can be found that all the analytic results fall in the range of corresponding experimental results except the results for stacking sequence $[90_2/0_2/(r_0)/0_2/90_2]$ and $[45_4/(r_0)/45_4]$, for which the analytic results (9.87 and 7.21 respectively) are close to the minimum experimental results (10.00 and 7.50 respectively). So the LSM is also effective to predict the resin pocket geometry around the microvasculature in composites.

Stacking sequence	Experimental results	Analytic results
$[90_2/0_2/(r_0)/0_2/90_2]$	10.00~11.25	9.87
$[75_2/15_2/(r_0)/15_2/75_2]$	9.05~10.00	9.53
$[45_4/(r_0)/45_4]$	7.50~8.75	7.21
$[30_2/60_2/(r_0)/60_2/30_2]$	5.95~6.50	6.06
$[15_2/75_2/(r_0)/75_2/15_2]$	5.65~6.45	5.91

Table 3: Comparison of experimental results and analytic results with $m_s = 4$. [12]

4 RELATION BETWEEN FSM AND LSM

In the FSM, tying 5 fibers in thickness direction together is equal to dividing a single ply into $h_l / 5l_f = 3.70$ sublayers, and tying 4 fibers in thickness direction together is equal to dividing a single ply into 4.63 sublayers. When a single ply is equivalently divided into 4 sublayers, the results of a^* for the FSM can be obtained by linear interpolation, as shown in Table 4. Comparing the results of two

methods, the differences are very small with a maximum relative error of -0.34%. The physical consistency of these two analytic methods is proved.

The fiber number m in the FSM and the sublayer number m_s in the LSM were set as 5 and 4 respectively based on the experimental result of a given stacking sequence in this paper. But in practice, the values of these parameters maybe relate to curing parameters and material properties such as curing pressure, resin viscosity and so on. The values of m and m_s may be different for other cases and need to be determined based on a few specimens. The complicated relation between the parameters and corresponding influence factors needs further study.

Stacking sequence	Results of method on the fiber	Results of method on	Relative error
	scale with a single ply equivalently divided into 4 sublayers	the later scale with a single ply divided into 4 sublayers	
[90 ₂ /0 ₂ /(r_0)/0 ₂ /90 ₂]	9.85	9.87	-0.20%
[75 ₂ /15 ₂ /(r_0)/15 ₂ /75 ₂]	9.52	9.53	-0.10%
[60 ₂ /30 ₂ /(r_0)/30 ₂ /60 ₂]	8.56	8.58	-0.23%
[45 ₄ /(r_0)/45 ₄]	7.20	7.21	-0.14%
[30 ₂ /60 ₂ /(r_0)/60 ₂ /30 ₂]	6.05	6.06	-0.17%
[15 ₂ /75 ₂ /(r_0)/75 ₂ /15 ₂]	5.89	5.91	-0.34%

Table 4: Comparison of results from two analytic methods with a single ply divided into 4 sublayers.

5 INFLUENCE OF STACKING SEQUENCE

In engineering practice, the stacking sequence of laminate may change. So its influence on the resin pocket geometry is discussed here with the FSM.

No.	Stacking sequence	Results	No.	Stacking sequence	Results
1	[0 ₄ /(r_0)/0 ₄]	10.55	8	[0 ₂ /15 ₂ /(r_0)/15 ₂ /0 ₂]	10.24
2	[15 ₄ /(r_0)/15 ₄]	10.19	9	[30 ₂ /0 ₂ /(r_0)/0 ₂ /30 ₂]	10.40
3	[30 ₄ /(r_0)/30 ₄]	9.14	10	[0 ₂ /30 ₂ /(r_0)/30 ₂ /0 ₂]	9.35
4	[45 ₄ /(r_0)/45 ₄]	7.46	11	[45 ₂ /0 ₂ /(r_0)/0 ₂ /45 ₂]	10.29
5	[60 ₄ /(r_0)/60 ₄]	5.27	12	[0 ₂ /45 ₂ /(r_0)/45 ₂ /0 ₂]	8.07
6	[75 ₄ /(r_0)/75 ₄]	2.73	13	[60 ₂ /0 ₂ /(r_0)/0 ₂ /60 ₂]	10.23
7	[15 ₂ /0 ₂ /(r_0)/0 ₂ /15 ₂]	10.51	14	[0 ₂ /60 ₂ /(r_0)/60 ₂ /0 ₂]	6.86

Table 5: Selected stacking sequences and corresponding analytic results of a^* .

The selected stacking sequences and corresponding results of a^* are shown in Table 5. The results of No.1 to No.6 are extracted and plotted in Figure 8. As shown in the figure, the width of the resin pocket decreases with the ply angle increasing, and the decreasing rate increases. This is because that the angle between fibers and microvascule decreases with the ply angle increasing, which can reduce the bending stiffness perpendicular to the microvascule of the laminate and reduce the size of the resin pocket. Besides, the curve in Figure 8 can be fitted accurately by the function $a^* = 10.55 \cdot \cos \theta$.

Figure 8: Results of No.1 to No.6 in Table 5.

Comparing the results of No.7, 9, 11, 13 with that of No. 8, 10, 12, 14 in Table 5, a conclusion can be drawn that for the similar laminates with same ply angles but different stacking sequences, the laminate with small angle plies locating close to the microvasculature has a larger resin pocket. This is because the bending stiffness of the plies with small angles can be better employed when they locate closer to the microvasculature.

Comparing the results of No. 1, 7, 9, 11, 13, when the ply angle of the plies away from the microvasculature changes from 0° to 60° , the value of a^* changes from 10.55 to 10.23 with the range of 0.32. However, comparing the results of No. 1, 8, 10, 12, 14, when the ply angle of the plies close to the microvasculature changes from 0° to 60° , the value of a^* changes from 10.55 to 6.86 with the range of 3.69. It can be concluded that the ply angle of the plies close to the microvasculature has greater influence on the resin pocket size than that of the plies away from the microvasculature. The size of the resin pocket depends largely on the plies close to the microvasculature. This is because the displacement field is assumed to vary linearly with respect to the thickness direction, and the bending deformation of the plies close to the microvasculature is larger than that of the plies away from the microvasculature.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, two analytic methods are developed to predict the resin pocket geometry around the microvasculature in self-healing composites with microvascular networks based on the principle of minimum potential energy. One calculates the bending strain energy on the fiber scale, and the other one is on the layer scale. Both methods can provide the closed-form solution for the width of the resin pocket, and the analytic results agree well with experimental results. The physical consistency of two methods is proved, and the influence of stacking sequence on the resin pocket geometry is investigated. Some conclusions are drawn as follows:

- (1) For the laminates with the same ply angle, the resin pocket width decreases with the ply angle increasing, and its decreasing rate increases.
- (2) For laminates with same angle plies but different stacking sequences, the laminate with small angle plies close to the microvasculature has a larger resin pocket.
- (3) The ply angle of the plies close to the microvasculature has greater influence than that of the plies away from the microvasculature. The size of the resin pocket depends largely on the plies close to the microvasculature.

The parameters (m and m_s) may relate to curing parameters, material properties and other factors, so they need to be determined based on a few specimens for other cases. The relation between the parameters and corresponding influence factors needs further study.

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